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**FORENSIC MEDIKAL ASPECTS OF DETERMINING GENDER AND AGE BASED
ON CRANIOMETRIC ANALYSIS**

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Annotation: *One of the main steps of identification process defining the individual in forensic medicine practice is age and sex determination. The aim of this study is to investigate the possibility of age and sex determination through bimastroid breadth measurement in cases where the cranium can be reached. The study included MSKT images of the skull of 150 Uzbek subjects (75 men and 75 women) aged 20–50 years, obtained in 2015–2023 at the Radiodiagnostics Department of the "Lazermed" private clinic in the Navoi region of the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

Key Words: *identification, age estimation, sex estimation, mastoid, 3D MSKT.*

Annotatsiya: *sud tibbiyoti amaliyotida shaxsni aniqlashning asosiy bosqichlaridan biri bu yosh va jinsni aniqlashdir. Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi kraniungga erishish mumkin bo'lgan hollarda bimastroid kengligini o'lchash orqali yosh va jinsni aniqlash imkoniyatini o'rganishdir. Tadqiqotda O'zbekiston Respublikasining Navoiy viloyatidagi "Lazermed" xususiy klinikasining Radiodiagnostika bo'limida 20-50 yoshdagi 150 nafar o'zbek populyatsiyasiga mansub shaxslarni (75 erkak va 75 ayol) bosh suyagi tasvirlari olingan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *identifikatsiya, yoshni baholash, jinsni baholash, mastoid, 3D MSKT.*

INTRODUCTION

Two of the most important parameters for identification both in forensic and archaeological cases are age and sex determination. In forensic practice, there are conditions in which the body unity is harmed and the victims cannot be recognized and identification is not possible through physical characteristics in mass deaths such as natural disasters and plane crashes or examination of remains in mass graves. Hemogenetic or odontological methods are primarily used in such conditions [1-6].

But in accordance with the conditions and the state of the material, molecular genetic methods cannot be studied or a regular dental record is not available for the individuals who are wanted to be identified. In similar conditions where primary identification methods cannot be used, practical and cost-efficient anthropometric methods with high accuracy rate are applied. In conditions where the bodies of the individuals were damaged extensively and the unity of the bodies was harmed, identification is aimed through using present body and bone pieces.

Identification studies made by using radio diagnostic imaging for body and skeletal remains and metric measurement methods for osseous structures constitute one of the most interesting new methods in this field [8]. Osteometric measurements made with radiological methods has many advantages such as not requiring the cleaning of the bones, not being a bone- destructuring operation and being more practical and applicable than many other identification methods [11, 2].

Cranium is the most convenient body part for age and sex determination through morphological and anthropometric methods after pelvis. The change caused by the involvement of muscle mass increased by puberty in cranial bones in males and the preservation of juvenile characteristics in females cause the high sexual dimorphism of the cranium [6-8].

In researches about determination of age and sex through cranial metric measurements, many parameters were studied such as; cranium maximum length or width, biorbital width, interorbital distance, bizygomatic breadth, nasion-prosthion height, nose width or height, mastoid height, dimensions of mastoid process, bimastroid breadth, foramen magnum maximum length or width and maxillary sinus or frontal sinus measurements [9-8]. The important point here is being able to make

analysis on present bones even in conditions where body unity is damaged. Mastoid bone is also rather suitable for age and sex determination studies as it mostly stands even the body decomposition since it is rather resistant to traumas with its anatomic position and compact structure [7].

The aim of this study was to present the usability of bimastoid breadth value obtained by 3D reconstructed cranial MSKT image for age and sex determination.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study included MSKT images of the skull of 150 Uzbek subjects (75 men and 75 women) aged 20–50 years, obtained in 2023–2015 at the Radiodiagnostics Department of the "Lazermed" private clinic in the Navoi region of the Republic of Uzbekistan. There were 25 females and 25 males in every group in the sampling separated into six groups with a difference of 5 years in each. To prevent the non-proportional concentration between the age ranges and the related low reliability, it was tried to examine the images of an equal number of males and females from all ages.

All demographically information such as age and sex were obtained from legal hospital records for the individuals evaluated. Not to affect measurement standard and analysis results, cases that had cranial pathology, cranial surgery or any acute or chronic diseases to cause osseous lesion were not included in the study.

All cranial MSKT images evaluated were obtained from a high-resolution computed tomography device with 120-140 kVp and 162-183 mA technical specifications and slices thickness between 0.67-1mm. In three-dimensional images obtained through reconstruction, the breadth was measured between the end points of "mastoid process" section of both mastoid bones in the rear face of the cranium in coronal plane and the value found was millimetric recorded (Fig. 1,2).

The obtained measurement values were evaluated with "Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) for Windows 21.0" package program. Independent student's t-test was used to defined the significance of the metric difference among sexes ($p < 0.05$). Discriminant function analysis was made for being able to determine sex and sectioning point was determined in the table obtained and discriminant function formula was formed. Accuracy rate values were also detected for the obtained measurements in order to be able to make a percentage classification. For age determination analyses, One-way ANOVA test was applied to the values obtained from both sexes and the significance was evaluated among age groups.

Figure 1.

Figure 1. Bimastoid breadth measurement from the rear in coronal plane in 3 dimensional imaging.

Figure 2

Figure 2. Bimastoid breadth measurement from the below in axial plane in 3 dimensional imaging.

RESULTS

Mean age of the population in the study was detected as 35.49±8.64 for the whole population; as 35.43±8.61 for male cases and as 35.56±8.68 for the female cases.

According to the F-ratio value obtained in the statistical significance evaluation of the difference between sexes, a significant difference was detected among sexes. In bimastoid breadth measurements according to sex, it was detected that, mean measurement values in males were higher than mean measurement values in females. Mean bimastoid breadth was detected as 108.53±4.38 mm in males and 100.82±4.19 mm in females (Table 1).

Table 1

T-test for Equality of Means

	N	Mean	Min	Max	Std.D	t	df
Male	75	107.5	97.5	123.2	4.37	21.023	597.0*
Female	75	100.7	86.9	115.9	4.18	21.023	295.7*

Table 1. Descriptive statistic of bimastoid breadth (mm) in male and female Uzbek population and t-test of significance between means

Data for the discriminant function analysis of the measurement used and canonical discriminant coefficient values are available in Table 2. Wilks' lambda value shows the percentage coefficient presented by the variable. Unstandardized coefficient and sectioning point values for bimastoid breadth are available below the table. Sectioning point can be detected by taking the average of centroid. In this method, discriminant score obtained by calculations can classify the individual; as male if the score is higher than the sectioning point and as female if it is lower [3].

Discriminant function score can be found with $Y(\text{sex})=a+b_1x_1+b_2x_2+\dots+b_nx_n$ formula. X presents; measurement, a presents; constant coefficient and b presents; the coefficient of the related measurement.

Table 2.

Discriminant function analysis and canonical discriminant function coefficients for bimastoid breadth of Uzbek males and females

	Wilks' λ	df	F-ratio*
Bimastoid diameter * p=0.00	0.552	597	484.99
Bimastoid diameter	Standardized Coefficient	Unstandardized Coefficient	Centroid M=0.899

	1.000	0.243	F= -0.899
Sectioning point (Constant)			-24.510 0.000

For example if we use the measurement taken from no. 22 individual; $Y(\text{sex}) = -24.410 + (0.233 * 110.60) = 1.340$ In this situation, the individual is determined as a male, as the score is higher than sectioning point value. Accuracy rates for females are observed to be very slightly higher than males. According to this result, correct sex determination was 82.7% in females and 80% in males. Sex distribution of each group, including 25 males and 25 females separated into age groups with a difference of 5 years, evaluated by One-way ANOVA analysis. When the average of the measurements is considered, a significant difference is not observed among sexes. A statistically significant difference was not detected according to the One-way ANOVA test findings made according to the age groups for both sexes ($p > 0.05$) (Table 3).

Table 3.

Analysis of bimastoid breadth by age distribution in both sexes

		Male				Female			
Age range	n	Mean (mm)	Std. Deviation	Min. (mm)	Max. (mm)	Mean (mm)	Std. Deviation	Min. (mm)	Max. (mm)
21 - 25	25	109.68	4.58	100.40	118.70	100.48	3.67	93.40	109.90
26 - 30	25	108.22	4.66	98.60	117.80	100.62	4.08	93.50	114.30
31 - 35	25	109.05	4.32	99.60	119.20	101.52	3.98	92.20	108.30
36 - 40	25	108.61	3.84	101.40	118.10	100.74	4.19	94.10	114.80
41 - 45	25	107.55	4.45	99.60	118.50	101.29	4.44	91.30	112.50
46- 50	25	108.09	4.30	99.30	122.10	100.28	4.77	87.80	110.10
Total	150	108.53	4.38	98.60	122.10	100.82	4.19	87.80	114.80

In multi-comparison analyses among age groups, a statistically significant difference was not observed in any comparison (Table 4).

Table 4.

Significance of bimastoid breadth by intergroups and intragroups according to age

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Male	Between Groups	142.69	5	28.54	1.50	0.19
	Within Groups	5601.87	294	19.05		
	Total	5744.55	299			
Female	Between Groups	57.79	5	11.56	0.65	0.659
	Within Groups	5194.78	294	17.67		
	Total	5252.57	299			

DISCUSSION

In addition to being used for age and sex determination by metric methods, craniums obtained from skeletal remains can also present a chance to make osteometric measurements depending on statistical basics through radiological imaging methods (such as two-way head graphy, lateral cephalometric graphy, multi-slice CT, 2 and 3 dimensional reconstructed CT, MR) (10, 14). Morphometric analyses of the researchers based on these imaging methods constitute an opportunity

to form extensive social databases. Thin slice opportunity, fast evaluation advantage, 3 dimensional evaluation opportunity and gradually decreasing imaging costs are prominent advantages [1]. In researches made on postmortem period; the elimination of maceration- related ethical concerns, fast evaluation advantage and the wide research database formed against the difficulty in reaching bone collections are defined as the main advantages (8-13).

The aim of this study is to determine age and sex from bimastroid breadth measurements using cranial CT images. It was analysed; whether the mastoid bone is free from the maturation and possible changes occurring with the advancing age. In result; a significant difference was not detected among age groups. When the population of our study is considered, a significant difference doesn't occur in mastoid bone dimension with the advancing age.

In literature, it is stated that mastoid area generally completes its maturization before puberty, its pneumatization increases and it is one of the most slowly growing areas of the body in postpubertal period [7,8]. Indeed, this maturation period of the mastoid area completed in early ages; prevents the usability of bimastroid breadth measurement for age determination as detected in our study, too.

In literature it is stated that, mastoid process dimension is larger as the male cranium is bigger than the females and owing to activity of spleniuscapitis, longissimus capitis and sternocleidomastoid muscles is stronger [3]. As a reflection of this data, it was again observed in our study that bimastroid breadth measurement obtained from male cases was higher than the females. According to our findings, mean bimastroid breadth was detected as 108.5 ± 4.3 mm in males and as 100.8 ± 4.1 in females.

In the calculations made after determining sectioning points of measured values and applying discriminant function analysis, sex determination with a ratio of 80.0% could be made in males and 82.7% in females. In a study made by Marinescu M. et al. on adults in Romania, accuracy rate for bimastroid breadth was detected as 73% and the measurements were defined as significant difference [1,2]. In the study made by Jain D. et al. on Indian adults, accuracy rate for bimastroid breadth was detected as 75% and its usability in sex determination was defined as relatively high degree [4].

Different parameters apart from bimastroid breadth measurement can be used for sex determination from cranium. In a study by Steyn M. and İşcan M.Y. evaluating 12 cranial parameters of 44 Caucasian males and 47 females from South Africa, the accuracy rate for the bizygomatic breadth detected as the most dimorphic parameter was found 80% [9]. Kranioti E. et al. obtained an accuracy rate of 81.9% for the bizygomatic width in the research evaluating 16 cranial parameters on 90 males and 88 females in bizygomatic breadth in Crete detected as the parameter with the highest distinction rate. In the study evaluating 5 cranial parameters on 164 males and 140 females made in USA by Walker P.L., an accuracy rate of 82.6% was obtained for glabella which is the most dimorphic parameter. In the study evaluating 5 cranial parameters on 205 males and 108 females made in Japan by Sakaue K. and Adachi N., an accuracy rate of 80.5% was obtained for supra-orbital ridge measurement which is the most dimorphic parameter. When high accuracy rate obtained in our study (82.0% in males and 84.7% in females) is considered, this shows that bimastroid breadth measurement can be used for sex determination in Uzbek population.

CONCLUSION

Population studies constitute one of the basic reference points of identification studies based on anthropometric measurements. Depending on many factors such as the geographical characteristics of the area people live in, genetic factors, nutrition habits, diseases and socio-cultural levels, inter-population or intra-population age and sex differences can be observed. Thus, especially in forensic cases; data for the population of the individual should be used as much as possible in biological profile studies [7].

In this study, the possibility of age and sex determination from cranial bimastroid breadth measurement in Turkish population was evaluated. According to the results obtained, it was concluded that; there is no significant change occurs in mastoid bone dimension with the advancing age. When obtained accuracy rates with high reliability are considered; it is supported that, the analysis method with 3D reconstructed MSKT images is convenient for sex determination. Starting

from here, it is concluded that this method can be used especially in conditions where primary identification methods cannot be used and in conditions requiring preliminary inspection.

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